

Table 2. Results of artificially inoculating rices with GM. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Rice	Tillers (no./hill)	GM-affected tillers (no./hill)	Affected tillers (%)	Infestation score
ACM18 (IET7804)	15	0	0.0	0
IET9688	17	3	17.6	7
IET9690	12	2	16.7	7
IR20 (susceptible check)	14	6	42.9	7
Surekha (resistant check)	13	1	7.7	5

The same three rices were tested under artificial conditions. Five unemerged galls were introduced into each caged plant. After 25 d, percentage of affected tillers was 7.7 in resistant check Surekha, 42.9 in susceptible check IR20, and 0 in ACM18 (Table 2). □

Screening rice varieties with different growth durations for spider mite *Oligonychus oryzae* infestation

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Sixteen rice varieties with short, medium, and long growth durations were transplanted in 4- × 4-m plots in the field during 1986 wet season. An aqueous suspension of spider mite *O. oryzae* containing 100 adults/250 ml water was sprayed on rice foliage 10 d after transplanting.

Severe mite infestation 40 d after spraying caused yellowing. Mite populations (eggs, juveniles, and adults) were recorded from a 10 cm² leaf area on 10 hills/plot chosen at random.

No test variety was free from mite infestation (see table). The mite population was highest in long-duration

Spider mite populations in rice varieties of different growth durations. Cuttack, India, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Parents	Duration ^a (d)	Mites ^b (no./10 cm ²)
Subhadra	TNI/SR26-13	90 S	18.9 a
Bala	N22/TN1	105 S	20.4 a
Kalinga-II	AC540/Ratna	80 S	28.2 b
Vani	IR8/CR1014	125 M	28.9 b
Parijat	TKM6/TN1	115 M	30.0 b
Kesari	Kumar/Jagannath	95 S	30.6 b
Sattari	Mut-Sel (NSJ200/Padma)	70 S	32.6 b
Pankaj	Peta/Tonkai Rotan	145 L	34.0 b
Savitri	Pankaj/Jagannath	155 L	39.6 c
Utkal Prabha	Waikoku/CR1014	155 L	40.5 c
Karuna	IR8/Adt 27	125 M	47.8 d
Jaya	T141/TN1	130 M	50.8 d
Jagannath	T141 mutant	150 L	53.4 d
Ratna	TKM6/IR8	125 M	60.2 e
Vijaya	T90/IR8	140 L	62.8 e
CR1018	Culture	155 L	70.5 f

^aS = short duration, M = medium duration, L = long duration. ^bMean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

CR1018 and lowest in short-duration Subhadra. Within the same duration group, some varieties showed significantly different populations.

Population differences were not significant between all varieties of one duration and all varieties of another duration. □

Leafhopper (LF) epidemic in Haryana

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Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* historically has occurred only as a sporadic and minor rice pest. But during the 1987 wet season (kharif), it struck in an epidemic intensity. Karnal, Kurukshetra, Ambala, and Sirsa districts were badly damaged.

Infestation started the first week of Aug and lasted to the first week of Oct. Peak infestation was during the second week

LF damage on rice in Haryana, India, 1987.

Variety	Tillers/hill ^a			Leaves/hill ^b			Length/leaf			Larvae (no./10 leaves)
	No.	Affected	%	No.	Folded	%	Length (cm)	Length affected (cm)	%	
Jaya	8.3	5.8	70	44.2 (6.72)	30.5 (5.31)	47	46.4	9.4	20	12.2
HKR120	10.3	10.1	98	51.7 (7.14)	51.5 (7.22)	100	37.2	19.0	50	18.2
PR106	8.9	8.6	97	44.5 (6.74)	42.8 (6.62)	96	42.4	24.6	58	13.5
IET8113	9.7	8.6	89	48.4 (6.96)	36.1 (6.00)	78	40.6	19.1	78	14.7
IET8116	12.3	11.0	98	51.2 (7.21)	36.2 (6.01)	85	39.6	15.6	62	15.7
Pakistan Basmati	14.4	14.4	100	67.2 (8.26)	66.0 (8.19)	100	71.9	60.6	84	52.0
LSD (0.05)	2.8	4.0		(0.60)	(1.75)		9.3	4.7		4.7

^aAv of 20 hills. ^bAv of 20 leaves. Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{n+1}$ values.

of Sep, when the rice crop was at the booting to panicle emergence stage. No variety was untouched, but varieties

with relatively broader leaves had less infestation. The pest caused 30-80% yield loss.

LF damage, affected tillers/ hill, folded leaves/ hill, affected length/ leaf, and larvae/10 leaves on 6 varieties were collected at HAU RRS during the second week of Sep 1987, when the attack was at its peak. Average temperature during this period was 22.8-

35.6 °C, humidity was 50-79%.

Jaya had minimum LF damage, Pakistani Basmati showed highly susceptible reaction to attack (see table). Medium-statured varieties in general had only 1 or 2 larvae/leaf; Pakistani Basmati averaged 5-6 larvae/ leaf.

Almost the whole leaf length (84%) in Pakistani Basmati was affected, compared to 20 to 78% in dwarf varieties. All leaves were damaged on HKR120, PR106, and Pakistani Basmati. □

Varietal reaction to rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino

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Remarkable differences in RWM damage were observed among 52 rice lines derived from 19 crosses and the check IR50 in the Cold Tolerant Variety Breeding Trial during 1985 dry season.

Each cultivar was transplanted in irrigated wetland in a 7-m² plot with 4 replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. No insecticide was applied to 60 d after transplanting (DT). RWM damage was estimated as total and damaged leaves in 10 plants randomly selected from each replication at 40 DT.

Eleven lines were found promising,

Reaction of rice cultures to RWM at DDR, Hyderabad, India.

Cultivar	Cross	Transformed means ^a (angular trans.)
RP2418-5	Ratna/Zagar	11.45 (3.9)
RP2419-3	IR36/Larbeoul	12.11 (4.5)
RP2418-10	Ratna/Zagar	12.90 (5.1)
RP2414-7	K39/VL 8	14.11 (6.0)
RP2415-7	IR36/IC47321	13.61 (6.0)
RP2419-2	IR36/Larbeoul	16.22 (8.1)
RP2418-4	Ratna/Zagar	17.74 (9.3)
RP1842-3	Jukoku/Rasi	18.51 (10.1)
RP1842-2	Jukoku/Rasi	18.62 (10.5)
RP2199-9	Phalguna/TKM6	18.83 (10.6)
RP2418-1	Ratna/Zagar	19.17 (10.8)
RP2235-200	Phalguna/IR50	42.93 (46.4)
IR50 (check)	—	24.65 (17.4)
Mean		18.53
LSD (0.05)		3.55
CV (%)		13.40

^aFigures within parentheses indicate the mean values of percentage damaged leaves over 4 replications.

with 10% or less damaged leaves (see table). The most promising were RP2418-5, RP2418-10, and RP2419-3 with 3-5% damaged leaves. In promising

lines, leaf damage ranged from 3.9 to 10.8%; highest was 46.4% in RP2235-200 (Phalguna/IR50). These lines are also cold tolerant. □

Excess water tolerance

CR 1009: suitable variety for waterlogged conditions

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In Kanyakumari district, particularly in Kalkulam and Vilavancode Taluks, rice is cultivated under waterlogged conditions in 7,000 ha. Local long-duration varieties Thattaravellai, Vallarakkan, Valsiromundan, and Saradi are low yielders, tall and thin stemmed, and prone to lodging.

Yield (t/ha) of four varieties under waterlogged conditions in nine locations. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Mean	Range
CO 42	132	90	5.3	3.1-6.7
Ponni	141	110	4.0	2.5-5.2
IET5656	132	94	5.2	3.4-6.6
CR1009	150	94	6.0	5.0-8.1
LSD (0.05)	—	—	0.6	—

We tested CO 42, Ponni, IET5656, and CR1009 in nine locations in farmers' fields. CR1009 (Pankaj/

Jagannath) recorded significantly higher mean grain yield, with a maximum of 8.1 t/ha (see table). It is 94 cm high, matures in 150 d, and has short bold white grains. □

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